

AMIR TEMUR GREAT COMMANDER AND FOUNDER OF AN EMPIRE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7791754>

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Abstract: *Amir Temur's mother was Mrs. Takina. His father, Amir Taragay, was considered one of the elders of the Turkic barlos clan and a notable leader of the Chigatoy clan. His ancestors ruled in Kesh region. Therefore, Amir Temur's father, Amir Taragai, was invited once a year to the congress of elders of the country called by the khan on the banks of the Ili River, and he regularly participated in such gatherings. At the same time, according to Sharafuddin Yazdi's emphasis, he was "mushfiq and kind to the ulama, sulaha, and muttaqi, and he used to go to their gatherings." ". Taragaijan Piri Shamsuddin Kulol was especially deeply respected. Later, sheikh Kulol Amir was Temur's elder. Taragaybek died in 1405. Amir Temur had an older sister, Qutluh Turkon, and a younger sister, Shirinbeka. They died before Timur and were buried in the mausoleums of the Shahi Zinda complex in Samarkand. "According to Mu'izz al-Ansab, Timur had three other brothers: Djuki, Olim Shaykh and Suyurghatmish. Timur had one uncle, whose name was Balta.*

Key words: *Homeland, Amir Temur, youth, activity, life, intelligence, power, war, people, movement, leadership, military, tax, invasion, Mongols.*

Amir Temur spent his youth in Kesh. When he turned seven years old, his father sent him to study. From a young age, Amir Temur was engaged in horse riding, hunting, archery, various other exercises and military games under the supervision of special coaches. At the same time, Amir Temur grew up to be a skilled horseman and brave horseman who could sort out vultures. Amir Temur was by nature heavy, compact, deep-thinking and perceptive and extremely intelligent, a person who quickly understood people's abilities, virtues, especially sincerity. Because of this, he was able to attract loyal friends among his peers even in his teenage years. His childhood friends and schoolmates (Abbas Bahadur, Jahanshohbek, Qimori Inoq, Sulaymonshohbek, Idiku Temur, Saifuddinbek, Hindushah, Qarkara, etc.) gathered around him, trained together, participated in competitions, gradually became skilled and joined a military group and formed a military unit. Later, they rose to the rank of commander in the army of Amir Temur. Amir Temur began his first military career by serving some regional amirs with his subordinates; participated in their mutual struggles, showed courage, trained in battles, and improved his military skills. His grain is spread over the entire Kashkadarya oasis. Amir Temur's intelligence, courage and fame brought him close to the influential amirs of Movarunnahr, amir Khizr Yasouri and amir Qazaghon. According to Khondamir, his father Amir Taragoi married Amir Temur first (1355) to Nurmushk Ogho, daughter of Amir Joku Barlos, and then in the same year (1355) O'ljoy Turkon, grandson of Kazaghan and sister of Amir Husayn, marries Ogo. Due to the subsequent marriage, an alliance was formed between Amir Temur and Amir Husayn, governor of Balkh, and they

fought together against the Mongols. Amir Temur's efforts to unify Movarounnahr began in the early 60s of the 14th century. At the end of the 50s of the 14th century, the struggle between the amirs intensified in Movarounnahr, and the amir Qazaghon was killed. The country has reached a peak of political confusion and severe tension. According to the information given in Khondamir's book "Habib ussiyar", the ulus was divided into about ten independent clans. In the Samarkand region, Amir Bayon is sulduz, in Kesh, Amir Haji Barlos, in Khojand, Amir Bayazid Jaloir, in Balkh, Uljoy Buga is sulduz, in Shibirgan, Muhammad I Khoja Aperdi Naiman, in Kohistan, Badakhshan Shah Amir Sotilmish, in Khuttalon, Kaykhusrav, in Hisori Shodmon region, Amir Husain and Amir Khizr Yasovuri consider themselves as absolute rulers. they announce.

During this period, the Mongol khans ruling the eastern part of the Chigatai ulus - Yettisuv and Eastern Turkestan took advantage of the difficult political situation in Movarounnahr and tried to establish their power here. Tughluq Temur from the Jeta Khans and his successor Ilyashoja invaded Movarounnahr several times in 1360-61 and 1365. The people's movement against the conquests and oppression of the Mongol khans begins. However, the amirs of Movarounnahr do not dare to lead the people and fight against the Mongol invaders. Some of them go to the side of the enemy, and the other part leave the country and seek refuge in other countries. Amir Temur's uncle, Amir Haji Barlos, the ruler of Kesh province, fled to Khurason. At such a difficult time, Amir Temur enters the political arena. 24-year-old Amir Temur, who took into account the unequal ratio of forces to oppose the Mongols, arrived at the beginning of 1360 with the beggars sent to Kesh by Tughluq Temur. As circumstances require, he goes to the khan's service and is appointed as a dorugasn of his province with his label. Undoubtedly, this was a political and strategic step taken out of desperation, with which Amir Temur got rid of another Mongol robber and saved the country and people from disaster. However, Ilyashoja, who was appointed as the ruler of Movarounnahr, and his commander-in-chief, Amir Bekkichik, and Amir Temur disagreed. For this reason, at the end of 1361, he was forced to leave the country.

To the south of Khiva, in the Urganji steppe, Amir Temur Tughluq meets with another opponent of Temur - his brother-in-law Amir Husayn. Amir Temur joins forces with him to fight the Mongols. At first, they fought with Tuqal (Tawakkal), the Khiva Daruga, who, according to the order of Tughluq Temur Khan, began to pursue Amir Temur. Then, in the fall of 1362, Amir Temur was injured in the right wrist and right leg in a conflict with the Mekronites, standing on the side of the regional ruler Malik Qutbiddin in Seistan.

Amir Temur and Amir Husayn fought several times with the army of Ilyashoja Chief Jeta during the next two years. Finally, at the end of 1364, they managed to expel the Mongol troops from the Movarounnahr area.

However, in the spring of 1365, Ilyashoja, who did not want to lose Movarounnahr, again marched on Turkestan. The battle between Tashkent and Chinoz is known in history as the "Mud Battle". They were defeated in the battle due to the treachery of Amir Husayn and retreated with their troops to the Amudarya and settled in Balkh region. Ilyashoja marched on Samarkand, capturing Khojand, Jizzakh and several other cities and villages without encountering any resistance. At that time, Samarkand could not resist a large army. The city had no walls, no strong fortifications, no armed soldiers. The bek and the emirs had left the

city, but the people rose up against the Mongols, and the generals took over the defense of the city. The defenders of the city are led by Mavlanozada Samarkandi from Madrasa student sciences, Abu Bakr Kuluyi (Kalavi) Naddof, the elder of wool (cotton) pickers' neighborhood, and Mavlana Khurdaki, a sniper. The Sarbadors dealt a crushing blow to the Mongols in the city of Samarkand. Ilyashoja was forced to leave Samarkand and then all of Movarounnahr. The news about the victory of the Sarbadars over the Mongols reached Amir Husayn and Amir Temur. Amir Temur spent the winter in Karshi, and Husayn on the banks of the Amudarya, and in the spring of 1366 they went to Samarkand. They stopped at Konigita and told them that they were pleased with the victory of the warlords over the enemy and that they wanted to meet them. However, when the leaders of the generals came to the emirs, Abu Bakr Kuluyi (Kalavi) Naddof and Maulana Khurdak Bukhari were hanged by the order of Amir Husain. Mavlanozada is Amir Temur. takes it to its protection and waits. In this way, the warlords were left without a leader and the rule of Amir Husain was established in Movarounnahr, but soon the relationship between Husain and Amir Temur became tense and turned into an open conflict. Amir Husayn, who was afraid of the increasing influence of Amir Temur, returned to Balkh and began to strengthen its fortress walls and fortifications. He also gathers a large army from Balkh, Kunduz and Badakhshan. Amir Temur, the head of Kesh and Karshi regions, is also preparing for a decisive battle against Amir Husain. Between 1366 and 1370, there were several conflicts.

Sayyid Baraka supported the activities of Amir Temur and presented him with a big drum, tabl and yalov, a symbol of supreme authority. Undoubtedly, this event had great political significance. Because it was a symbol of royalty. Amir Temur understood this well. That is why, before reaching Balkh, he held a council with the emir and his followers in Orpuz region. Suyurgatmish, a descendant of Genghis Khan, was placed on the throne of the kingdom of Movarounnahr by the will of the majority and according to the laws of that time. Until the army of Amir Temur reached Balkh, new forces joined him along the way. At the same time, most of the emirs left Amir Husayn. Amir Husayn's troops were defeated in the battle, after a two-day siege, on April 10, 1370, Balkh sh. Amir surrendered to Temur. Amir Husayn was captured and executed. After this victory, Amir Temur married Saraymulk, the daughter of Kazan Khan, the Genghisian ruler of Movarounnahr. In connection with the marriage of the Khan's daughter, Amir Temur received the title "Koragon", that is, "son-in-law of the Khan". On April 11, 1370, in the congress held with the participation of all the begs, emirs, governors of regions and districts, Sayyids (sons of God) of Termiz, as well as Amir Temur's comrades-in-arms, who had been with him since his youth, and the elder Sayyid Baraka, according to tradition, Suyurgatmish Khan was declared the ruler of the country. In practice, the central government was managed by Amir Temur himself, and the power in the regions was managed by his sons, grandsons and close amirs. Samarkand became the capital of Amir Temur's state, and in the summer of the same year, the city wall and fortress were restored, palaces and palaces were built.

In order to strengthen the political and economic position of the country, to put an end to the internal disunity that has been going on for a long time, and to establish peace and tranquility, Amir Temur called a great congress in Samarkand (in June 1370). The issues of formation of the central state system and creation of the army were discussed there.

Amir Temur, who well understood the importance of military power in managing the country, attached great importance to the structure of the army. He introduced high-ranking military titles such as "Amir" and "Amir ul-Umara". While reforming the army in military terms, he pays special attention to the selection of commanders and their training, the order of military units and their location, the arming of servants and soldiers, and issues of discipline (see also Military art of the Timurids).

When Amir Temur came to power, he first of all regulated the tax system in order to eliminate the severe economic crisis in the country. He called upon the amins, kalontars and tax collectors to be honest and fair with the raiyat and not to act against the law when collecting state taxes, because the stability of the kingdom largely depends on the condition of the raiyat, his loyalty to the state and the head of the state. The protection of the subject is strengthened by the law, the law is equal to all. Amir Temur protected not only his own people, but also the inhabitants of conquered countries as much as possible. He saved them from captivity and looting.

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